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SOME ASPECTS OF THE ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE PAKHTACHI DISTRICT

Abstract. *In recent years, the leadership of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been implementing several comprehensive measures to diversify the regional economy, modernise industry and agriculture, create new production facilities, and improve social infrastructure. Pakhtachi district is one of the regions that is rapidly developing in the process of these general reforms. This article analyses the indicators of the agricultural and industrial sectors in the economic development of the Pakhtachi district based on statistical data.*

Keywords. *Pakhtachi district, GDP, rural economy, infrastructure, Zarafshan River, labour resources.*

Introduction. According to the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, today, 49.0 per cent of the population of our republic lives in rural areas, and 3.3 million people, or 22.8 per cent, of the economically active population are directly engaged in agricultural production. This makes the study, assessment and rational use of the economic potential of rural areas one of the urgent issues⁷¹.

It serves to implement the tasks set out in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3182 dated August 8, 2017 “On priority measures to ensure the accelerated socio-economic development of regions”, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 222 dated April 28, 2022 “On additional measures to ensure the comprehensive socio-economic development of the territories of the Samarkand region and further

⁷¹ stat.uz - Data from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

improve the living standards of the population in 2022-2026”, and other regulatory legal acts related to this activity⁷².

Literature review. The founder of the direction of rural geography within socio-economic geography in the Commonwealth of Independent States is Professor S.A. Kovalev from Moscow State University. In his candidate and doctoral theses, as well as in several scientific monographs and articles from 1946 to 1963, S.A. Kovalev established rural geography as a distinct scientific discipline and developed its research methodology. Subsequently, notable research in this area has been continued and is ongoing by scientists such as B.S. Khoreyev, A.I. Alekseyev, I.K. Orfanov, T.G. Nefyodova, E.E. Leyzerovich, O.S. Rusinova, and others.

Geographical aspects of the socio-economic development of rural areas in Uzbekistan- explored by Z.M. Akramov, R. Valiyeva, E. Tashbekov, G.R. Asanov, O.B. Ata-Mirzayev, Yu.i. Akhmadaliyev, E.K. Umarov, A.S. Soliyev, A.A. Kayumov, M.I. Nazarov- are highlighted in their scientific works. The rural areas' issues during the years of independence have been examined by R.Y. Mahamadaliyev, M.I. Nazarov, and A. Sattorov as part of their candidate theses. Specific rural administrative districts served as case studies in the scientific research of K. Gadoyev, J. Musayev, and H. Omonov.

Main part. Pakhtachi District, situated in the Samarkand region of the Republic of Uzbekistan, was established on 9 February 1935 as part of the territory of Narpay District under the name Pakhtakor District. In 1963, it was re- integrated into Narpay District. However, on 12 April 1973, it was separated again as a distinct district, adopting the name Pakhtachi District.

Pakhtachi District is known for its rich history, natural resources, farming traditions, and hardworking inhabitants. It borders Narpay District to the east, Nurabad District to the south, and Khatirchi, Karmana, and Navbahor Districts of Navoi Region to the north, north-west, and west. The district covers an area of 1. 1.37 thousand square kilometres. Its population stands at 155, 000 residents (2025). The district comprises 7 towns (Ziyaudin) and 59 mahalla citizens' assemblies. It is located 140 kilometres from the regional centre. The Zirabulak and Ziyovuddin mountains, part of the Zarafshan range, divide the district into two parts: the vast, unirrigated Karnab Desert and the northern, irrigated left- bank plain of the Zarafshan Valley. The Zarafshan River flows through the northern part of the district from east to west. Due to its low bed, pumping water is challenging. The Narpay Canal, with over 370 branches, is used to irrigate crops, and water in the steppe area is supplied by pumps.

The economy of the district primarily focuses on agriculture- particularly cotton, grain, and melon cultivation- and livestock farming. There are also enterprises in the industrial, transport, and communication sectors. In 2024, our President acknowledged that "due to the correct implementation of work in the

⁷² Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026”. January 28, 2022, No. PQ–60.

localities, the volume of industry in 25 districts and cities has increased by more than 10 per cent." Notably, Pakhtachi was among the regions experiencing rapid industrial growth. Additionally, 325 kilometres of drinking water networks were laid during this period, which is significant for boosting the district's economic potential and enhancing residents' living conditions.

Pakhtachi District contributes 2.1 per cent to the industrial output of the Samarkand region (see Table 1). In 2024, industrial production in the district increased by 108.6. 6 per cent, reaching 1. 1.1 trillion soums. In particular, this growth pertains to the main product types, but the detailed breakdown is not included here.

Figure 1. Volume of industrial production in Pakhtachi district.

Currently, 130 industrial enterprises are operating in Pakhtachi district, of which 6 are large and 124 are small business industrial enterprises, 37 of which were established in 2024. In 2024, 39 projects worth \$37.9 million are planned to be implemented in the industrial, agricultural and service sectors, thereby creating more than 1,700 new jobs. To attract foreign investment funds, 6 foreign investment projects worth \$135.3 million have been formed in the district. Of this, \$64.5 million in direct foreign investments and loans are planned to be absorbed, and \$8.2 million in foreign investment funds were absorbed in the first months of this year.

Table 1
Share of districts in the volume of industrial production in the Samarkand region (in per cent of the total)

	2010- year	2015- year	2020- year	2021- year	2022- year	2023- year	2024- year
Samarkand region	100,0						
Samarkand city	59,7	46,6	44,0	44,8	45,7	45,0	36,3
Kattakurgan city	2,5	2,4	2,2	1,7	1,4	2,3	2,4
Akdarya	1,9	2,1	2,5	2,6	1,9	2,2	2,3
Bulungur	0,8	2,8	2,6	2,3	2,3	2,2	2,3
Jambay	3,5	9,2	11,8	11,4	11,0	9,8	8,6
Ishtikhon	2,2	2,1	2,0	2,3	2,1	2,2	1,9
Kattakurgan	3,0	2,1	2,5	2,4	2,0	2,1	4,1
Kushrabat	0,7	1,0	0,4	0,4	0,4	0,4	0,4
Narpay	4,5	3,1	3,0	2,5	2,4	2,6	2,2
Payarik	2,7	2,5	2,2	2,1	2,1	2,0	1,7
Pastdargam	3,5	3,7	4,2	3,7	3,6	3,3	3,0
Pakhtachi	2,4	1,7	2,1	2,1	2,0	2,5	2,1
Samarkand	4,8	6,6	7,3	7,8	6,8	6,8	6,6
Nurabad	0,4	0,8	1,2	1,2	1,5	1,6	1,2
Urgut	5,8	10,3	8,5	7,5	7,1	7,4	8,7
Taylak	1,8	3,2	3,6	5,4	7,7	7,4	6,9

If we analyse the work on increasing the income of the population in economic figures, the volume of industrial products amounted to 749.7 billion soums at the end of 2023, compared to 206.7 billion soums in 2021. That is, the volume of industrial products increased by 3.6 times. In addition, the volume of industrial products per capita in 2021 reached 1.4 million soums, and by the end of 2023, it reached 5 million soums. The total number of registered small business entities in 2024 (excluding farms) was 596, compared to 1,416 at the end of 2023.

It is planned to create 21,954 permanent and seasonal jobs in the district in 2023. In practice, this figure amounted to 31,052, ensuring employment for unemployed and underemployed citizens. Also, within the framework of the family entrepreneurship development program in the district, 70,159 billion soums of preferential loans were allocated to 3,214 unemployed citizens.

Conclusion. Shortly, it is advisable to take into account the following for the economic and social development of the Pakhtachi district:

- The diversification of industrial sectors in the district is low. Shortly, it is important to build and launch new mining and industrial enterprises here, due to the

intensive implementation of complex mining and geological exploration work in the district.

- It is known that the district is famous for its vegetable growing. In the future, it is necessary to increase vegetable plantations and process them on the spot. Therefore, it is necessary to organise modern greenhouses for growing vegetables in the district, build processing enterprises based on the latest modern technologies and export them directly to the world market. It is necessary to further develop the volume of exports and imports and attract new investors.

- develop the building materials industry in the district by re-modernising kaolin, quartz, granite, gypsum deposits located in the territory of Karnabota and other neighbourhoods and increasing their extraction volume;

- Based on the specific natural climatic conditions of the district, it is advisable to develop the horticulture, fruit and vegetable growing, and melon growing sectors of agriculture here. Also, the large areas of pastures within the district's land fund make it advisable to develop such areas of animal husbandry as cattle breeding, sheep and goat breeding, and beekeeping.

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